

Structural Performance Evaluation of a Tall Building with Bracings and Base Isolation Using ETABS Software

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Abstract- The safety of people inside a building depends on its ability to withstand seismic waves and survive an earthquake with minimal damage and repairs, and without collapsing easily. Various systems are used to absorb seismic energy, including dampers, seismic isolation devices, earthquake-resistant walls, and underground water tanks. The effectiveness of these systems depends on their type and location. In this study, the seismic analysis of a 16-story G+ residential building is carried out based on the analysis of the dynamics of floor shear stress and overturning moment. The ground motion dynamics data are taken from the PEER database. Based on the maximum floor shear stress and maximum overturning moment, the performance of transverse bracing and seismic isolation structures is compared with that of conventional moment structures. By placing these elements at the corners of the building in different models, an efficient and adequate model is obtained..

Index Terms- Analysis of change dynamics, floor displacement, floor overturning moment, struts, rubber-lead bearings.

I. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic forces like wind and earthquakes significantly affect buildings. Seismic design aims to prevent structural failure and minimize damage, ensuring occupant safety and reducing economic losses [1]. Energy dissipation systems such as dampers, isolators, and other non-structural elements help control excessive vibrations [2]. Among seismic protection methods, bracing systems, base isolation, and dampers are the most effective [3]. Studies highlight the efficiency of transverse bracing and lead rubber bearing (LRB) isolation systems in mitigating earthquake forces [4]. Earthquakes generate inertial forces in buildings, causing shear and overturning moments, especially at floor levels [5].

1. Earthquake Analysis

Seismic analysis evaluates how a structure responds to earthquake forces and is essential for seismic design and retrofitting, especially in high-risk zones [6]. Advanced software tools simulate earthquake impacts using fine time steps and real-world physics, similar to gaming engines [7]. These simulations help assess complex buildings like the Osaka International Convention Center using specialized seismic elements placed in the foundation or throughout the structure [8].

2. Earthquake-Resistant Design

Earthquake-resistant structures aim to reduce damage during seismic events. While no design can entirely prevent damage, codes require structures to withstand probable maximum earthquakes and remain functional during frequent smaller

events [9]. The goal is to ensure life safety and reduce structural and non-structural failures [10].

3. Base Isolation Systems

Base isolation is a highly effective seismic mitigation technique, especially for buildings on stiff soils [11]. It reduces seismic ductility demands by inserting flexible elements—typically elastomeric or sliding isolators—between the structure and foundation. These isolators allow controlled lateral movement and extend the structure's natural period, reducing seismic energy transfer [12]. Conventional isolators often use natural rubber with low damping properties [13].

4. Principles of Seismic Isolation

Seismic isolation alters the building's response to reduce ground motion transmission. In ideal cases, a flexible structure avoids acceleration, absorbing ground displacement [14]. Practical systems must still support vertical loads.

Effective isolation requires materials that provide:

- Flexibility (candy)
- Displacement capability
- Resistance to vertical and operational loads

II. METHODOLOGY

Reinforced concrete buildings are significantly affected by dynamic loads from earthquakes. To mitigate this, a seismic isolation system was evaluated using the response spectrum method. A 3D structural analysis was carried out in ETABS, initially modeling the building with fixed foundations, and

then with rubber base isolators installed between the superstructure and substructure. The performance of the isolation system was assessed by comparing both models.

To meet the design objectives, the following tasks were defined:

- Determine isolator dimensions to achieve the required period shift and reduce seismic forces.
- Calculate the damping coefficient to keep structural displacement within design limits.
- Define the distribution of support properties and construction elements for seismic Zone V.
- Compare results for fixed-base and isolated-base RC buildings in Zone V to evaluate effectiveness.

ETABS allows you to model the structure using a simple tool, “Quick Model” as shown in Figure 1, which allows you to define a grid along the X, Y and Z axes. In this example, we have created a symmetrical model by placing 6 sections along the X axis and 6 sections along the Y axis, with a uniform spacing of 4.5 m along the X axis and 5 m along the Y axis. We consider a R+16 structure with a standard floor height of 3 m and a minimum floor height of 3 m

Figure 1 Quick model for a new model

Determine the Seismic Loads as per IS 1893:2016 Part

Figure 2 Seismic load

Run Model Validation for both Cases using ETABS

Figure 3 Model verification

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The three cases considered in this study were evaluated based on the parameters of story displacement, period, story shear, base shear and torque to understand the behavior of the high-rise structure G+16 under similar loading conditions.

Figure 4 Offset per floor (mm)

Figure 5 Time interval in seconds

Shear force (kN)

Figure 6 Shear force (kN)

Basic Shear Force (kN)

Table 1 Baseline Shift

Basic shear force (kN)		
Normal structure	Seismic isolation construction	X-shaped design
4598.098	3021.983	3342.076

Figure 7 Base shear force (kN)

Torsion kNm

Table 2 Torque (kNm)

Torsion kNm		
Normal structure	Seismic isolation construction	X-shaped design
11766,73	6643,88	7721,92

Figure 8 Couple (kNm)

IV. CONCLUSION

Lateral Displacement

Lateral displacement is critical in structures exposed to seismic or wind loads. Taller buildings tend to be more flexible and thus more susceptible. Studies show that conventional buildings experience 32.21% more lateral displacement than base-isolated structures and 30.98% more than X-braced buildings. This indicates that base isolation combined with bracing effectively limits lateral movement.

Natural Period

The natural period refers to the time a structure takes to complete one cycle of vibration. Base-isolated buildings have the longest natural period, followed by braced structures, while conventional buildings have the shortest. A longer natural period helps reduce seismic forces acting on the structure.

Storey Shear

Storey shear is the lateral force acting at each floor due to seismic or wind loading. Lower stiffness reduces storey shear. In conventional designs, the top-floor shear was 29.8% and 27.45% higher compared to isolated and braced structures, respectively, indicating better performance of seismic mitigation systems.

Base Shear

Base shear is the total lateral force acting at the base during seismic activity. Conventional buildings showed higher base shear than those with seismic isolation and bracing—by 29.71% and 26.87%, respectively—demonstrating the efficiency of these systems in reducing seismic demand.

Torsion

Torsion refers to twisting in structural elements caused by seismic or wind forces, often coupled with bending and shear. Seismic isolation reduced torsional moments by 51.82%, while bracing reduced it by 42.19% compared to conventional fixed-base structures, significantly enhancing stability under asymmetric loading.

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